

ROTOSCILLOMBRAGE— THE CONSTRUCTION AND ARTISTIC APPLICATION OF A COMPUTER CONTROLLED LOUDSPEAKER ARM.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents Rotoscillombrage, a project exploring the artistic and technical applications of a motorized rotating loudspeaker arm used for room-scale feedback music. Developed as part of the Moving Loudspeakers residency at the Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology (ICST) in Zurich, the system functions as both a spatialization tool and a generative sound synthesis device.

The paper details the mechanical and digital design of the system, addressing challenges in motor control, real-time sound interaction, and spatial feedback. A key focus is the use of site-specific modeling techniques to simulate and refine spatial audio behavior, enabling composition of situated feedback music in the absence of continuous physical access to the installation site.

The project resulted in both a concert and an installation, demonstrating how controlled loudspeaker movement interacts with acoustics to create emergent musical structures. By integrating real-time compositional strategies and dynamic spatialization, Rotoscillombrage contributes to contemporary discourse on kinetic sound art and spatialized electronic music. This work underscores the potential of moving loudspeakers as an expressive medium, expanding the relationship between sound, space, and motion in live performance and installation contexts.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes the ideation, construction, and use, of a large electronically controlled motor-driven rotating arm, that positions and points a loudspeaker as a mode of spatialization and synthesis of electroacoustic feedback music. The arm was conceived of and constructed to create *Rotoscillombrage*, a piece that was presented both as an installation and in a concert form, at the *Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology* (ICST) at the *Zurich University of the Arts* (ZHdK), as a part of the Artist in Residency track *Moving Loudspeakers* [1].

The work started in 2022 and finished with a concert and a period of exhibition in early 2024.

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This paper will present the design considerations, summarize the most important learnings from constructing the physical and digital parts needed, discuss the musical implications of the work, and the specific techniques developed in modelling, composing, and performing for and with Rotoscillombrage.

The paper structure is as follows. The Background section will contextualize the work by presenting the research context, the hosting institution, as well as the background of the participating artists, as well as related work. The next section, Rotoscillombrage, will describe the system components, and detail the most important findings and techniques developed to realise the work. In Section 3, The Modelling Process, all the different forms of modelling used to make the composition process possible are described and discussed. In Section 4, Artistic Outcomes, a brief summary is given of the artistic results of the project with links to available documentation. In Section 5, Reflections, the process and results are discussed. Finally, in Conclusions, the most important learnings are summarized and some directions for future work are laid out.

2. BACKGROUND

In this section, the relevant context that the work presented was produced in will be presented, as well as the artistic precursors that inspired the directions taken as well as related work by other researchers and artists in the field.

2.1 utrumque

Rotoscillombrage is situated in a longer line of works that deal with similar concerns and materials in various ways. While a full description of these works is beyond the scope of this paper, referencing them provides useful context that can be added to trace the lineage of the ideas and techniques presented here.

Several previous projects combine and intertwine installation and concert modalities where the installations often figure in a concert-like way and the performances tend to put the performers in a reflective pose, joining the audience in exploring the spatial qualities as they unfold with the possibility of adding interventions that are more performative. This includes *Work* commissioned by the *Elevate Festival* in 2023¹ and the *St. Elisabeth Song Cycle* com-

¹ youtu.be/gRtXWdCDJR0?si=1-8uQJSqZYS_ji_k

missioned by the *Labor Sonor Festival* in 2021.

Single-point spatializations or directed sound projections can be found in *nullibidem* - where open speakers were moved around manually as a synthesis gesture, *Rundgång* - a piece that rotates a sound source around the audience by using single pairs of speakers in the GRM Acousmonium loudspeaker orchestra, *Andacht* - a piece that shot out beams of sound from an IKO Speaker² in a highly reverberant environment to create cascades of reflections. More information on all pieces and full recordings can be found online³.

2.2 Related work

Rotating loudspeakers emerged in the 1950s to address practical challenges in sound production. Initially, their primary purpose was to create sound modulation rather than simulate movement or positioning. For example, the *Leslie loudspeaker* (1940) [2] added modulation effects like Doppler shifts [3] and amplitude variation to Hammond organs, while the *Gyrophonic Projector* (1948) [4] replicated the spatial dynamics of pipe organs by rotating the entire speaker. Hermann Scherchen's *Nullstahler (zero radiator)* (1954) [5] was an attempt to achieve even sound distribution and spatial clarity in monophonic recordings.

It was only with their adoption in artistic contexts that rotating loudspeakers evolved into tools for sound movement and spatial positioning. This shift was marked by works such as Pierre Boulez's *Poésie pour pouvoir* (1958) [6] [7] and Karlheinz Stockhausen's *Kontakte* (1958) [8] [9], which utilized these devices to explore dynamic sound movement and spatial interaction as integral compositional elements. Although Edgard Varèse briefly employed a rotating loudspeaker in *Poème électronique* (1958), he soon replaced it with a newly developed electronic amplitude-panning circuit [10].

Initially vital for acoustic effects, rotating loudspeakers became less essential with technological advancements. Innovations like John Chowning's computer-calculated sound paths (1971) [11] and advancements in studio tools enabled the simulation of sound movement and positioning, reducing reliance on mechanical systems. Today, moving loudspeakers are a distinct artistic tool, appreciated for their unique spatial and acoustic impact in select works.

The Institute for Computer Music and Sound Technology (ICST) has a long-standing focus on moving loudspeakers, reflected in the course *Composing with and for Moving Loudspeakers* and the concert series *Sound in Motion (SIM)* [12], which showcases student works. The research project *Sound Moving Sources* [13] [14] builds on this foundation, exploring technical and artistic aspects, developing tools for precise movement control, and investigating creative applications where moving loudspeakers act as autonomous agents in performance.

The ICST's Artist in Residency program, *Moving Loudspeakers* [1], has invited—and continues to invite—established artists to incorporate moving loudspeakers

into their work. In doing so, it advances spatial sound practices and draws on the center's educational and research expertise to foster artistic innovation.

Rotoscillombrage continues the tradition of rotating loudspeakers on booms, evolving from works like Gordon Monahan's *Speaker Swinging* [15] and Ray Lee's *Ring Out* (2017) [16], which used manually swung or spun speakers. Motorized systems further developed this approach, as exemplified by Edwin van der Heide's *100dB@100Km/h* (2000) [17], where a dynamically rotating loudspeaker attached on a boom adapted to audience presence and positioning.

Bridget D. Johnson's speaker.motion (2016) [18] system explores rotation and tilt as parameters for live spatialization and provides a structured setup for their real-time use—elements that are also central to *Rotoscillombrage*.

Andres Bossard's *Rotobossophon* [19] and Peter Kutin's *Toros#1* (2019) [20] featured similarly dynamic and spatially adaptive rotations. In contrast, *Rotoscillombrage* emphasizes the reflections and resonances of the space itself, rather than reacting to audience presence.

As such, *Rotoscillombrage* is more related to the ecosystemic approach of Di Scipio [21] and even more so to the work of Di Scipio and Sanfilippo [22] where the authors reject the idea of extracting data in favor of channeling and directing energies present in the audio signal to derive new signals useful as control inputs to signal processing components. Refraining from injecting a symbolic layer of classification and instead staying with the audio-rate signals is an important aesthetic understanding of the work where synthesis and composition become inextricable. The notion of intervening in such feedback systems in a guiding capacity, shaping rather than controlling, is eloquently formulated by De Campo as gaining influence by losing control [23].

Rotating loudspeakers have evolved from practical tools to essential artistic devices that shape spatial sound experiences. While advancements in audio technology replaced their original functions, their unique physical interaction with space and sound perception remains irreplaceable. Contemporary approaches emphasize precise movement control and environmental responsiveness, highlighting their role as autonomous agents in performances and their capacity to merge technical innovation with artistic expression. The resulting complexity requires careful consideration of the systems as a whole and special care must be taken when devising both compositional strategies and interfaces with which to perform with them.

3. ROTOSCILLOMBRAGE

In this section, the technical aspects of *Rotoscillombrage* will be laid out, divided into two subsections that deal with the hardware and software components respectively.

3.1 Hardware

A rotating rod has been designed to allow a speaker to move in a large circle while it rotates itself. The

² iko.sonible.com/en.html

³ www.utrumque.com

construction (see Fig.1) consists of a ceiling suspension (A) that houses the drive for the vertical axle, to which the boom (C) is attached. The speaker (B) is mounted at one end of the arm, while two counterweights (G1, G2) are attached to the opposite end. Apart from the truss parts and the speaker, the mounts for the rod and the speaker are custom-made.

Suspension and drive of the arm (A): The suspension system (see Fig. 2, A) supports and drives the arm using a seamless steel pipe (A1) centered by a guiding tube (D). At the top, a welded steel plug (A2) with a T-surface distributes load via a rolling bearing (C) and prevents sliding. A smaller tube (A3) passes through the plug and a 12-pole slip ring (G) for uninterrupted power and signal transmission. At the lower end, a rectangular bracket (B) secures the boom with screws and rubber wedges. The structure, mounted on two steel plates, attaches to the ceiling with four TV-spigots (K). A stepper motor (E) powers the axle via a toothed belt (F) with a 3:1 ratio, while a radial ball bearing (L) stabilizes the upper axle.

Arm (C): The seven-meter-long arm (see Fig. 1) is built using the Global Truss F22 2-point truss system [24]. It consists of two three-meter segments (a) and one one-meter segment (b), connected by conical pins. A rotatable speaker is mounted at one end, with two counterweights—one fixed (G1) and one adjustable (G2)—at the opposite end to ensure precise horizontal balance.

Earlier tests with 50 mm aluminum and steel tubes (3.5 m length), fixed at one end and freely hanging at the other, revealed vertical oscillations in the tube and horizontal vibrations during acceleration. These disturbances disrupted rotation and posed a risk of damaging the mechanism. To address this, the chosen two-point truss effectively eliminated vertical deflections and minimized horizontal vibrations, with counterweights ensuring stability. Due to the weight and to prevent oscillations, acceleration and deceleration had to be performed slowly. A three-point truss was avoided to maintain a lightweight, unobtrusive design.

Suspension with rotatable speaker and drive unit (3): The design (see Fig.2, B) resembles the arm mount but is smaller due to the lower weight. The loudspeaker (L) is mounted in a frame (R) suspended on a steel axle (A1) running through a gliding tube (D) for vertical centering and a 6-pole slip ring (G). A T-shaped sleeve (A2) transfers the speaker's weight to an axial ball bearing, while a stepper motor (E) drives the axle via a toothed belt (3:1 ratio). A radial ball bearing prevents lateral movement, and a power unit (H) supplies motor current. The construction attaches to the arm's lower tube with two couplers.

Loudspeaker (L): The Genelec 8030A, a compact bi-amplified loudspeaker with a weight of 5.6 kg [25], was selected for its frequency response of 55Hz to 20kHz and its excellent low-frequency performance. Integrated

screw threads allow for secure mounting within the frame. The Directivity Control Waveguide™ (DCW™) technology [26] provides precise sound projection, ensuring clear and balanced audio reproduction. During rotation, the loudspeaker dynamically projects sound across the surrounding space, blending direct sound with evolving reflections. This interaction continuously shapes both timbre and perceived loudness, emphasizing the acoustic effects introduced by the rotational motion.

Motor (E): Two Trinamic stepper motors are used: the PD60-4-1160-TMCL for the boom and the PD60-3-1160-TMCL [27] for the loudspeaker. These motors feature integrated controllers, support up to 51200 microsteps per revolution, and communicate via an RS485 serial interface, allowing both motors to share a single two-wire cable.

The boom system, weighing 45 kg with a total moment of inertia of 339 Kgm², achieves stable rotation at up to 5 rounds per minute using a 9.3 Nm torque (3:1 gear ratio). The loudspeaker system, with a moment of inertia of 0.28 Kgm², rotates effortlessly with 6.3 Nm torque. Both motors use gentle acceleration curves to prevent oscillations, vibrations, or damage to the drive system during motion transitions.

Noise is minimized by cutting motor power during standstill and insulating the loudspeaker motor with foam. The toothed belt drive reduces rigidity, enabling smoother and more flexible motion under dynamic conditions.

The developed system enables a loudspeaker to rotate within a large circular area while maintaining stability and smooth operation. The lightweight two-point truss minimizes deflections and vibrations, with counterweights ensuring proper balance. Stepper motors with optimized settings and configurations reduce noise and deliver smooth motion, while additional noise reduction is achieved through foam insulation and power cut-off during standstill.

3.2 Software

The software components in this project were made with the SuperCollider programming language with some Python utilities running in parallel to SuperCollider for facilitating the serial motor control. The motor control software performed seemingly simple tasks, but it became a somewhat complex piece of software. While the motor's internal safeguards (detailed above) made sure the motor never did anything that might damage it, triggering those safety mechanisms meant that the resulting behaviour was hard to predict, e.g. how long it would take to move from one speed to another. This was a musical challenge, as there were many physical constraints to what a motor could be tasked to do at any given moment, depending on the rotational forces at that time and the inertial strain on the system, that might modulate the execution of a timed gesture so that it could potentially miss its mark. Furthermore, the pops and creaks from the rig itself, most prominent when the system was asked to move at the limits of its capabilities, were deemed undesirable and the motor control software was written to avoid them as far as possible.

Figure 1. Overview. A: Suspension and drive of the rod; C: arm; B: Suspension with rotatable speaker and drive; G1, G2: Counterweights

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the (A) suspension with drive and suspensions for the arm and (B) speaker suspension with drive.

X1: Connection from/to main part with Power (230V), RS485, balanced audio signal. X2: Connection with 8 cables for Power (230V), RS485, balanced audio signal to the loudspeaker part. X3: Connection to the loudspeaker with Power (230V) and balanced audiosignal.

The final set of governing limitations were such that one could set the desired speed to anything from full speed to stand-still, *from* any ongoing rotation from full speed to stand-still, and the motor control software would ramp between them in an appropriate manner that kept the physical rig running quietly, smoothly, and without strain on the motors. This was achieved by tuning three separate limiting systems:

- A linear crest factor-limit that simply clipped the maximum rate of change for the motor speed for each iteration of the control loop.
- A proportional factor limit that limited the rate of change to a fraction of the current motor speed.
- An exponential lag that mainly limited the rate of

change when moving between very slow speeds, or from stand-still, when the relationship between the inertial weight of the system and the motor torque was strained and the motor needed to ramp up very slowly to get the mass of the arm moving.

Whichever limiting system that imposed the lowest limit would constrain the motor speed at that time, and if none of the limits were reached the motor speed was left unaffected.

Besides some more general processing blocks for e.g. controlling level dynamics (mainly sustainers and compressors) and adjusting the spectral content (e.g. filters and equalizers) the central musical component used was a circular graph we call *Node Rings*. The nodes in the Node Rings contain relatively simple processing, it can be as little as a filter and a nonlinearity, e.g. a wave folder. The edges of the Node Ring are the same for each node, meaning that they create interlocking patterns that repeat. If all nodes have an edge to the next node, a simple circle appear. If each node has an edge to the node two steps forward, a more intricate weave appears. In the Node Rings used for Rotoscillombrage, each node had several edges making for very complex graphs with simple elements. The microphones in the space could be injected at different points in the graph and one or several outputs could be extracted and played back in the room.

As all Node Rings shared the room as a component in their feedback path, they all interacted in complex ways when played at the same time. Sometimes one Node Ring would completely suppress another, sometimes they could form an interlocked third system with musical properties that clearly distinguished it from its two constituting graphs.

The digital signal processing presented a huge parameter space for control with several hundred parameters. Therefore we opted for a high level control of interpolating between several pre-composed parameter settings or *states*. Because of the interaction in the room and the impact of the arm, even playing a known state could lead to surprising results. And when interpolating between states, linearly, using normalized parameter values, there were no guarantees to find interesting or even sounding multi dimensional points on all intermediary interpolations between states.

4. THE MODELLING PROCESS

Modelling was central to structuring the work, as access to the site with the arm mounted was only possible for a total of two weeks out of the year of development and compositional work. Many characteristics of the site, e.g. the room geometry and its resonances, the loudspeakers and microphones used, and especially the arm itself, would have a big impact on the type of feedback-based music that make up the practice of the composing authors (Eckel and Elblaus). For this reason, a series of models, physical and digital, in various fidelities using several different techniques were created. The models provided a variety of insights and material useful in different stages of the process. The specific process will be described in this section. For more details on general uses of modelling as artistic practice we refer to a previous paper by the authors on the topic [28]. For the purposes of this paper, our understanding of modelling can be summarized as the construction and interaction with a set of systems that all relate to a specific site by exposing some aspect of that site in some fidelity that is useful in furthering the experiential act of composing something specific to that site. Site, in turn, is the final full digital, electro acoustic and room acoustic target of the composition process.

Before our first on-site visit, we started experimenting off-site with physical setups that worked as guides for us to narrow the scope of possibilities. At this time, little was decided about the space we would end up in, what technical solutions would be possible and most of all what musical possibilities that could be reached. These early experiments included hanging speakers, moving speakers around manually, both cabled systems and high quality Bluetooth speakers that allowed for more radical motion. When coupled with simple well-known feedback systems these experiments highlighted the qualities of the moving as it influenced our repertoire of feedback-based signal processing and it gave us a refined sense of what to expect in terms of how our musical systems would respond to movement in a wider range of speeds and distances than what we had previously attempted.

During the first visit, we decided on where to place the arm and made many decisions about the characteristics on the arm itself. We then repeated some of our off-site experiments with manual movement of several kinds of physical loudspeakers in the chosen room, allowing us to understand the interplay between the room acoustics and the speaker and microphones. From this we could make measurements with loudspeakers of a narrow variety of size and power in combination with tentative mic positions. This allowed us to have a sounding reference, a digital simulation using convolution that would allow us to run musical material through the acoustics of the space, including the speakers and microphones, and even set up real-time systems that incorporated some of the acoustic properties of the space. While the relationship between the measured speakers and microphones were still clearly different to the projected end results, some of the more particular characteristics of the space like the spectral characteristics of the reverberation and a prominent flutter echo between oppos-

ing walls in the long direction of the room could be clearly represented and made use of in the composition process.

The next step was to use and evaluate our tentative plans for the arm by using a digital shoe-box simulation of the room with a moving loudspeaker in it. Knowing the dimensions of the room and having the measurement to compare with when tuning the dampening of the reflections we could produce a convincing model using the *IEM Plugin suite*⁴. This allowed for the development of the motor control code, with which we could simulate moving the arm and rotating the speaker by sending Open Sound Control messages from SuperCollider to the plugin to further estimate the impact of movement and gauge the relation to the resulting rate of change in different feedback systems. Using the combination of SuperCollider and the shoebox model controlled from SuperCollider, a new form of adaptivity was possible, where a feedback system could be set up so that SuperCollider could play into the room-speaker-simulation, listen to what came back, and then make decisions on how to move the virtual speaker depending on the characteristics of the sound, which in turn affected the resulting sound of the feedback loop. This model was still an imprecise representation of the actual site and more a general estimation of a room of that size, but it offered a very high fidelity of control with cybernetic feedback possibilities on the level of the automation of the motors.

The final model used was an interpolated multi-measurement model that offered both specific measurements of the site and a kind of estimation of the effects of the moving speaker. On the second visit, the arm was in place in the room and as such the site was complete. Once the microphone positions were decided, a series of N sine-sweep measurements were taken that covered a small discreet subset of the practically infinite continuum of possible speaker positions. To simulate the movement of the speaker, an equal-power panning through the set of convolutions was used, each loaded with the impulse response of the measurements of the consecutive speaker positions and this way an estimate of not only the exact positions, but also the movement space implied between them, could be offered.

This modelling process supported a year of composition work that would have been impossible, or at least wildly speculative without it. The final model had a surprisingly rich fidelity in that running the same software programs through the model and on site the resulting behaviors of the programs was very similar. Of course, they would never sound exactly the same, which is often also true for running the same program twice at different times on site, but their dynamics and character were similar enough for them to function as identical components of composition.

This is essential to the modelling practice. Allowing for some phenomenological precognition that affords a good experiential estimation of a future that has not yet come to pass. Having an environment that is rich and detailed enough for artistic hunches to actually be informed and likely to pay off is what makes the rather complex task of structuring the interaction of several site-specific feed-

⁴ <https://plugins.iem.at/>

back processes possible. The kind of artistic modelling described in this section is a multifaceted production of experiential knowledge that covers different aspects of what is modeled, with the goal of finding and using characterful qualities that can inform the composition of a piece that integrates the site into its very core.

5. ARTISTIC OUTCOMES

While the project generated a wealth of artistic material during its year long run, there were two main artistic outcomes. A concert and an installation. The concert was three quarters of an hour with the audience seated below the arm inside its circumference in standard concert seating (see Fig.4). The installation was open for six days with the audience being free to come and go as they pleased and either sit on some asymmetrically placed chairs and plinths or move around freely in the space (see Fig.3). The two versions of the piece used the same software and compositional material, and differed in how the material was selected and controlled. As described in Section 3.2, the method of real-time musical control of the system was twofold: picking and interpolating between parameter sets, or *states*, and controlling the motors.

In the installation mode, Rotoscillombrage was set up so that the physical rotation of the arm and the speaker corresponded to the state interpolation using integer factors or divisors. The installation moved through a series of fixed-time segment, and for each segment a rotation speed for the arm and for the speaker was chosen from a composed set. Then, two ratios were selected and applied to each motor speed to arrive at two frequencies that are some multiple or division of the physical movement of the arm in the space. These two frequencies were then used to produce a Lissajous figure, where the ratio of the rotation of the arm decided the x-position and the ratio of the rotation of the speaker decided the y-position in a two-dimensional interpolation space with a state in each corner. Since the state interpolation and the position of the speaker both contribute to the resulting sound, the installation created undulating patterns that were the combination of four sinusoidal gestures locked in an small integer frequency relationship that was both audible and visible.

For the concert, the arm moved according to a fixed score of directions and speeds, showing most of the movement possibilities in the duration of the performance, while leaving room for the needed time for acceleration and deceleration. Starting from almost imperceptible shifts that produced very slowly varying comb filtering, to very dramatic fast movements of the speaker through the space while rotating at high speeds. The two performers, Eckel and Elblaus, with two MIDI-controllers each, used rotary encoders with push button functionality for activating the states and weighting the state interpolation (see Fig. 4). Pressing a knob activated a state and added it to the multi-point-interpolation that was made between all active states, weighted by the rotary position of the knob. This allow for both abrupt and very gradual gestures, as the rotary encoders can be made to be very fine, moving many orders of magnitude beyond what a 7-bit MIDI controller can do.

A video of the full concert is available online⁵ and there is also a video recording of an artists' talk by the performing authors⁶ that explore more of the artistic implications of this work.

6. REFLECTIONS

The arm is a prototype developed from experience gained in earlier motorized loudspeaker projects. Its precise, position-controlled stepper motors minimize the need for complex control programming, making the system particularly suitable for artistic applications. Safety was a key consideration: four TV spigots or two couplers ensure structural stability, and the axles are designed to prevent slipping or disengagement.

The modular design allows for quick assembly, disassembly, and transport; the longest component measures only three meters. During setup and teardown, two additional supports stabilize the structure, as the central axle is not built to withstand lateral loads. Cable routing via a multi-core system simplifies installation, though caution is required when handling the 230-volt power supply to the speaker. The construction is maintenance-free thanks to sealed and permanently lubricated ball bearings. The system is ready for performance after a short audio check and motor calibration.

The use of incremental modelling made interactive determination and exploration of the site's characteristics possible. Especially noteworthy was the successful use of mixing measurements of discreet loudspeaker positions to provide an approximation of a continuum of movement. In review, it turned out to be a very telling and useful approximation of the situation attainable through relative modest means.

Regarding the spatialization, and its role in room-scale feedback systems, single point projection can produce a rich and varied sound field and is both spatially interesting and a subtle and particular synthesis component. However, it is clear that a single point spatialization operates as an excitation system for the space it is in, and as such, beyond the primary radiation of the speaker itself, it is only as interesting as the variation it is able to excite. While the arm was a system of quite some complexity, especially mechanically, having the speaker only rotate or only move was tried as a subset of the possible movement patterns, and was also very rich, meaning simpler rigs are probably very useful as well. Some of the richness is lost however in recording, because of how the movements of the listener, from subtle shifts of the head to actually walking through the space, are so important to produce the full experience. This is also true for the digital models that suffer from a static position that is unchanging in a way that a person present in the space could never reproduce. Still, the method that provided the best imaging and preserved the experience of being in the room to the highest degree was the binaural recordings made with the Neumann KU100 artificial head. The Schoeps MSTC 74 ORTF microphone

⁵ www.youtube.com/watch?v=fW5QweNOR6k

⁶ www.youtube.com/watch?v=xuq677AyE0U

Figure 3. The Rotoscillombrage installation.

Figure 4. The Rotoscillombrage concert setup.

that has been the preferred choice in previous productions sounded good but had a different balance between the static reverberant parts of the room acoustics and the beam from the speaker, but these results are to be treated as preliminary until more systematic testing can be done.

Interpolating between composed parameter sets gives tactile and immediate connection to vast parameter spaces that influence chaotic system with emergent behavior and hysteresis. Having known fixed points with more predictable spaces in between made for a good balance of predictability and curious exploration. Paired with the dominating influence of the arm, having the option to not interpolate, or at least stay very close to a known state exposed the variation that the site provided.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This technical and artistic review of the Rotoscillombrage project is an attempt to offer useful knowledge for others who are attempting similar projects. The authors would like to draw special attention to the suspension designs that were the results of long iterative processes of refinement and testing. The practical example of the use of

modelling to compose site-specific work with limited access to the site, and the positive result of interpolating between several convolutions is also a strong finding that validates previous work. The multi-point state-interpolation through the high-number-dimensional parameter space is a useful technique to compose for and perform with musical systems with a high level of complexity. Finally, we hope to add to the tradition of room-scale acoustic feedback systems that fuse the notions of music as organized time and music as organized space, highlighting a situated site-specific approach to computer music and a novel spatialization technique.

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